

Fecal microbiome transplantation as a means of multidrug resistant bacterial decolonization of the intestine

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Summary

The partial or complete imbalance of the intestinal microbiome, as a consequence of extensive antibiotic use, can establish a number of pathological conditions, including colonization with multidrug resistant bacteria, which can subsequently lead to severe infections. Therefore, the attempt to restore the microbiome to its prior condition is an approach that can be used supplementary to other therapeutic options. This procedure can be performed through fecal microbiome transplantation (FMT), a method that is being used effectively in treating recurrent *Clostridium difficile* infection. Several studies have indicated that FMT can effectively eliminate the carrier status of ESBL producing Gram-negative bacteria in up to 40% of the patients. Furthermore, fecal transplantation was able to de-colonize patients from vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* as well as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. In addition, this method may be a therapeutic option for antibiotic-associated hemorrhagic colitis. However, as the ap-

plication of this methodology in research protocols is very recent and the reports are scarce, more studies are required in order to establish the actual effectiveness as well as the safety of FMT in multidrug resistant bacterial de-colonization.

Key words

microbiome, dysbiosis, fecal transplantation, microbiome transplantation, multidrug resistant bacteria

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Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance has been defined as one of the most critical threats to human health.¹ Recent reports indicate that the rate of infections due to multi- and pan-resistant bacteria, which have limited therapeutic options, increases rapidly in certain areas of the world,² exceeding the rate of research and development of new antibiotics.¹ Studies for *Klebsiella* isolates producing carbapenemase have shown that these infections are associated with higher rates of sepsis.^{3,4} Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) infections are associated with worse clinical outcomes and vancomycin-resistant *Enterococci* (VRE) are associated with increased morbidity and mortality.⁵

Antibiotic resistance in bacteria can be mediated through chromosomal or transmissible (e.g., plasmids, transposons, integrons, etc.) genetic elements.¹ Chromosomal mediated resistance is usually species-specific and can be difficult to transmit. The complex diversity of the transmissible genetic elements however is a reservoir of resistance that can be easily acquired through colonization and then spread to neighboring bacterial cells, especially under the pressure of antimicrobial therapy. This usually happens within the microbial communities of the human body, especially the intestine.⁶ Such colonization mainly occurs in the health care facilities from direct person-to-person spread between health care workers and patients.¹ In that respect, the early detection of potential carriers

and their isolation, followed by decolonization efforts, is of critical importance.

The microbiome is referred as the entire microbial community of a given habitat, the genetic information it contains and the environment it interacts with.⁷ All surfaces of the body that come in contact with the environment, such as the skin, gastrointestinal tract, urogenital tract and respiratory tract, are colonized by microorganisms and affect the composition of the microbiome.⁸

The intestine microbiome is a major part of the body's immunological system, being a mechanism that prevents colonization and infection from pathogens.¹ In addition, it provides support for the nutrient production within the gastrointestinal tract. Developments in the methodology of sequencing of microbial genomes have provided new evidence for the role of gut microbiome in health and disease, and a growing list of diseases characterized by unique changes in the composition and function of microbiome has been described.⁹

Although there is no agreed definition of a healthy gut microbiome, high overall microbial diversity, stability and performing of important functions, have been established as the key indices of the healthy state.⁹ This balance of the microbial ecosystem is called eubiosis and is a fundamental concept, while dysbiosis is defined as an ecosystem in which bacteria no longer interact together and with the host in mutual harmony.¹⁰ While many potential confounders

(e.g. diet, drugs, exposure to pathogens, host hygiene) can affect microbial composition, it has been shown that microbial dysbiosis can alter intestinal permeability, normal function and the metabolic profile, thus potentially leading to disease status.¹¹

One of the main procedures of gut microbiome alterations is antimicrobial chemotherapy, which minimizes diversity and selects for limited numbers of resistant bacterial clones. For example, exposure to meropenem, cefotaxime and beta-lactam-clavulanic acid combinations reduces the abundance and the diversity of the intestinal microbiome, while administration of vancomycin and gentamicin increases the expression of genes associated with resistance to these antibiotics.¹² Administration of fluoroquinolones and β -lactams for seven days can significantly reduce microbial diversity by 25% and core phylogenetic microbes by 58.6%.¹³ Administration of ampicillin and gentamicin derivatives to infants for 4 weeks was also associated with a significant increase in *Proteobacteria* levels and a decrease in *Actinobacteria* in feces.¹³

In that respect, a healthy intestinal microbiome is critical for the welfare of the patient, and a clinical approach to restore it to the previous condition seems to be attractive from the therapeutic point of view.¹ The main current treatment strategies for this restoration are (1) the oral administration of probiotic bacteria which may displace potentially pathogenic bacteria and promote the balance of the microbial community, (2) the oral administration of prebiotic agents which preferentially or exclusively are metabolised by probiotics to ensure their overgrowth and (3) the oral administration of combinations of probiotics and prebiotics (synbiotics).¹⁴ Other therapeutic approaches that are being explored include phage therapy, fecal microbiome transplantation (FMT) and bacterial consortia transplantation (BCT).¹⁴

In the following mini-review we will address the FMT methodology and explore the current research as a potential tool to address the multiresistant colonization of the intestine.

Fecal microbiome transplantation procedure

Fecal microbiome transplantation (FMT) is the transfer of slightly modified feces, from a donor, into a patient's gastrointestinal tract to improve dysbiotic status and restore microbial function by increasing overall diversity.⁹ Thus, the goal of transplantation is to restore eubiosis, through the rehabilitation of microbial populations.¹⁵ The transplantation consists of collection, preparation and storage of the sample as

well as the proper preparation of the patient before and after treatment.¹⁵

The procedure has several variations, but the main points are (a) mixing feces with a bacteriostatic liquid, (b) removing extra matter and (c) delivering donor feces to the patient.¹⁶ Feces can be injected via several methods, either through colonoscopy or from the upper gastrointestinal tract. Both these methods have individual benefits and risks.¹⁶ To prevent contamination from the environment, feces are collected from the donor to a fecal collector.¹⁵ The minimum amount of stool for administration from the lower gastrointestinal tract is 25 gr, while from the upper is 12.5 gr.¹⁷ Feces are mixed with normal saline, shaken and passed through a filter to remove large particulate matter.¹⁶ Glycerol is added as cryopreservative in a final concentration of 10% in a total final volume of 200 ml per sample, thus allowing the samples to be stored at -80°C for up to six months without losing their clinical effectiveness as compared to fresh material.^{15,18}

Although at present, the only consensus clinical recommendation of FMT is for the treatment of recurrent *Clostridium difficile* infection (CDI), a number of trials worldwide are exploring other possible therapeutic indications, including eliminating MDR colonization.⁹

Multi-resistant Enterobacterales

Extended-spectrum beta lactamase (ESBL) is a group of enzymes that can hydrolyse penicillin and cephalosporin group antibiotics and as a result render these antibiotics ineffective.¹⁹ *Enterobacteriaceae* with ESBL genes cause ineffective treatment of infections and they are associated with higher mortality, longer hospital admission and higher medical expenditures.¹⁹ These bacteria can be isolated from any clinical specimen, including urine, blood, lower respiratory tract, etc.¹⁹

In a series of 15 patients with ESBL intestine colonization, all patients underwent FMT procedure.¹⁹ The first attempt succeeded in decolonizing three patients,¹⁹ whilst a second attempt on seven of the remaining 12 succeeded in decolonizing three more, resulting in an overall eradication success rate of 40%.¹⁹

A recent case report described the eradication process of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* in a patient with end-stage renal disease consequent to recurrent episodes of pyelonephritis.²⁰ After hospitalization for the removal of the damaged kidney, colonization was established, so he underwent FMT that resulted in decolonization that was permanent at 12-weeks follow-up, thus allowing him to be placed on the waiting list for renal transplantation.²⁰

In a series of renal transplant patients with recurrent urinary-tract infections (UTI) due to ESBL producing Enterobacterales following renal transplantation, FMT was performed to eradicate the colonizers from the intestine.²¹ A few days after the infusion of donor feces, a single relapse of UTI was reported,²¹ but during the 12 months follow up, no further episodes occurred,²¹ thus concluding that FMT might be an effective treatment in renal transplant recipients with recurrent UTIs caused by intestinal colonization with MDR bacteria.²¹

However, in a randomized trial of immunocompromised patients, intestinal colonization rates by ESBL and carbapenemase producing Enterobacterales did not decrease in the group of patients that were treated with antibiotics and FMT as compared to controls that received only antibiotics,²² thus indicating that the issue might be multifactorial.

Vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* spp.

Vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* (VRE) is a pathogen with major effect in healthcare.²³ VRE infections are mainly reported among critically ill, transplant and immune compromised patients.²³ VRE colonization has also been associated with CDI, as both share common risk factors and VRE colonization has been reported together with CDI in numerous studies,²³ as there is evidence that antibiotics disturb the microbiome and favor the selection and the expansion of resistant bacteria.²³

A study of 11 patients with VRE colonization reported that after FMT eight of them were successfully decolonized.²³

A case report of a female patient with orthotopic cardiac and single cadaveric kidney transplants complicated by multiple episodes of VRE infections and CDI after the transplantation, that underwent FMT, resulted in both CDI treatment and successful VRE eradication and the results were stable after a one-year follow-up.²⁴

Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is a major source of hospital-acquired infection.²⁵ Throughout the years MRSA infections have been associated with the increased perioperative use of antibiotics, especially beta-lactams.²⁵

A single study, with five patients, reported that all patients before FMT presented with decreased intestinal flora, of which half were *Staphylococcus aureus*.²⁵

After FMT the gut microbiome was similar with the donors' microbiome, *S. aureus* was eradicated and no patient presented with symptoms indicative of MRSA enterocolitis.²⁵

Antibiotic-associated hemorrhagic colitis (AAHC)

Antibiotic-associated hemorrhagic colitis (AAHC) is usually seen, after penicillin treatment, as partial, often inhomogeneous hemorrhagic colitis and predominates in the right colon.⁸ In AAHC patients increased isolation of *Klebsiella oxytoca* resistant to β -lactamases has been reported as well as production of the enterotoxin tilivalline, which leads to intestinal epithelial apoptosis and colitis.⁸ A number of severe cases of apoptotic enterocolitis have been reported after combination treatment using antibiotics and steroids, presenting with severe exhaustion of the microbiome, while in extreme forms can lead to severe acute Graft versus Host disease.⁸

In a single case of AAHC, FMT was used to restore the intestinal microbiome and was effective in reducing epithelial cell death and enterocolitis.²⁶

Conclusions

The human microbiome is in constant interaction with the host. Dysbiosis changes in the microbiome can be reverted to the previous eubiosis status using different procedures, such as the use of antibiotics, probiotics, prebiotics and combinations of these. Studies have indicated FMT as an alternative treatment; FMT has been extensively studied for CDI and has been incorporated into everyday clinical practice as a consensus procedure. During the last five years, several other options have also been explored, including the eradication of MDR colonization of the intestine. Although different studies, mainly against Enterobacterales, have been published indicating promising results, their number thus far is limited, and in that respect a definite conclusion cannot be reached yet. Thus, more studies on the effectiveness on FMT against MDR colonization are urgently needed, as well as long term monitoring for the safety of FMT on these patients.

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Περίληψη

Η μεταμόσχευση του εντερικού μικροβιώματος ως μέθοδος για την εξάλειψη του αποικισμού του εντέρου από πολυανθεκτικά βακτήρια

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Η διαταραχή της ισορροπίας, μερική ή ολική του εντερικού μικροβιώματος, λόγω της χρήσης αντιβιοτικών μπορεί να οδηγήσει σε πληθώρα παθολογικών καταστάσεων, αλλά και αποικισμό του εντέρου από πολυανθεκτικά βακτήρια που μπορεί να οδηγήσουν σε λοιμώξεις δύσκολο να αντιμετωπισθούν. Ως εκ τούτου η προσπάθεια αποκατάστασης του μικροβιώματος είναι μία θεραπευτική προσέγγιση που μπορεί να δράσει συμπληρωματικά στην σύγχρονη θεραπευτική. Η διαδικασία αυτή μπορεί να πραγματοποιηθεί μέσω της μεταμόσχευσης κοπράνων, μία μέθοδος που ήδη χρησιμοποιείται για την αντιμετώπιση της υποτροπιάζουσας λοίμωξης από *Clostridium difficile*. Μελέτες έχουν διεξαχθεί κυρίως για φορεία Gram-αρνητικών εντεροβακτηριακών που παράγουν ευρέως φάσματος β-λακταμάσες (ESBL) και η μεταμόσχευση κοπράνων πέτυχε έως και 40% την εκρίζωσή τους. Επιπλέον, η μεταμόσχευση κοπράνων απήλλαξε ασθενείς από την εντερική φορεία ανθεκτικού στη βανκομυκίνη εντεροκόκκου ή και ανθεκτικού στη μεθικιλίνη *Staphylococcus aureus*. Τέλος, αυτή η μέθοδος μπορεί να είναι μια θεραπευτική επιλογή για την αιμορραγική κολίτιδα που σχετίζεται με αντιβιοτικά. Ωστόσο, επειδή η εφαρμογή της τεχνικής είναι πρόσφατη και οι σχετικές δημοσιεύσεις είναι λίγες, απαιτούνται περισσότερες μελέτες για την αποτελεσματικότητα αλλά και της ασφάλειας της συγκεκριμένης προσέγγισης.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

μικροβίωμα, δυσβίωση, μεταμόσχευση κοπράνων,
μεταμόσχευση μικροβιώματος, πολυανθεκτικά βακτήρια

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